

Techno-Orientalism: Artificial Intelligence and the “Other”

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This short paper interrogates the concept of Techno-Orientalism as a critical framework for understanding the sociopolitical and cultural implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) development (see further, Adib-Moghaddam 2025). It situates the discourse within the historical construction of the “West” as a hegemonic entity, a narrative deeply entangled with the material and ideational presence of the “East.” By deconstructing the Eurocentric assumptions underpinning AI systems, the paper highlights how these technologies perpetuate racial and cultural hierarchies, treating race as an essentialized rather than socially constructed category. In a final step, I argue that AI ethics must be grounded in a recognition of shared humanity and the interconnectedness of local and global identities, with localized cultural symbolism.

Critical scholars have introduced the term “Techno-Orientalism” to accentuate techniques of exclusion engendered and galvanized by AI systems. In an important compilation of articles, some of these critical scholars link Techno-Orientalism to representing Asians and Asia itself in stereotypical fashion as technologically adept, yet intellectually underdeveloped and therefore in need of Western tutelage (Roh et. al. 2015).

In this way, Techno-Orientalism refers to the representational practice in which the East — particularly East Asia—is imagined through hyper-technological futures: roboticized societies, opaque digital authoritarianism, and alien forms of intelligence. Therefore, Techno-Orientalism continues older orientalist patterns, but now through the lens of technological imaginaries: The “Other” becomes a speculative laboratory for Western anxieties and desires about automation, surveillance, and posthuman futures.

Rather than capturing the realities of everyday life in non-Western societies, techno-orientalist narratives encode geopolitical fears—of Iran’s cyberwarfare, China’s AI dominance, Japan’s robotics economy, or South Korea’s digital culture—into fantasies that justify “Western” moral superiority, much in the same way traditional Orientalists deemed themselves a part of a civilizing mission (Adib-Moghaddam 2023). That cultural blindness towards the “Other,” which is an essential feature of the Western narrative, has not changed with the shifts in global power away from Europe and the United States.

Traditional and Techno-Orientalism

As the late Edward Said famously argued, traditional Orientalism depicted the peoples of the “East” as essentially backward because of their alleged racial inferiority (Said 1979). With the resurgence of Asian power centered around China, this attitude was very difficult to hold. Therefore, traditional orientalist attitudes transmuted into depicting Asians as “essentially robotic automata.” The process of othering typically relies on descriptions that deny the “Other” cultural agency or “civilizational” prowess. Asians may be successful, but they are only “capable of fine-tuned execution and coordination, but lacking the sort of individual creativity and spirit that defined the Western subject” (Kim 2022). Hence, a process of othering continues as the “West” represents “platforms in China as something inferior, different, or even morally depraved” (Yang 2023).

Techno-Orientalism thrives precisely through affect: it animates fantasies of threatening or technological futures that justify geopolitical anxieties. What I have called “the myth of good AI” relies on such civilizational claims—casting Western tech as rational and benevolent, while depicting non-Western tech as opaque or dangerous. Said would accentuate, via the French philosopher Michel Foucault, that such myths are systems of knowledge that naturalize power (see further Adib-Moghaddam 2012). In other words: Techno-orientalism and good-AI narratives mask who benefits from AI systems and who becomes vulnerable through them—elevating certain actors (big-tech, Western states) while rendering others (Global South users, marginalized communities) invisible. Wendy Hui Kyong Chun (2019) agrees: Such “high-tech Orientalism” safeguards a “white hegemony”

over the definition of what it means to be “human,” reiterating a racial hierarchy that rationalizes the exploitation of the “Other.” We may add that such techno-racism is largely a technique to safeguard Western dominance from the re-emergence of Asia as a locus for global power.

There is an important conceptual lesson to learn here. The idea that AI is a force for “good,” neutral, or civilizationally beneficial operates as a myth that masks its political embeddedness. This myth requires three interdependent ideological moves that must be identified as essential techniques of obliteration: First, the purification of AI from its human, institutional, and corporate origins. Second, the cleansing of the dominant discourse about AI from the “Other,” and third, the erasure of structural harm, such as algorithmic discrimination, surveillance capitalism, and militarized automation. In this way, AI is framed as a pedagogical or civilizing tool—an extension of the “West’s” enlightenment project—while the real actors shaping AI systems, in particular private firms, security institutions, and states, remain abstracted away, safe and secure from public scrutiny and, most crucially, from legal accountability. In summary, then, the myth of good AI purifies a polluted and dangerous technology, creating the mirage that AI is apolitical, neutral, even benevolent, and an essential technology for human improvement. The harms that AI does on an everyday basis, conceptualized in the emerging critical AI studies corpus as algorithmic racism, surveillance capitalism, and labor exploitation, are treated as accidental glitches, rather than systemic features of AI technology.

Techno Co-Constitutions

So far, I have argued that “Western” AI is not

only a technical assemblage, but a cultural and (geo)political power project. When “Western” AI is imagined as “good,” it is repeatedly tethered to “Western” discursive and epistemological superiority. When the “East” (or the Global South) is imagined as hyper-technological, Asia becomes an object for Western fantasies and subjective imaginations, rather than a site with its own political, social, and cultural agency and complexity. Hence, the myth of good, “Western” AI reveals itself as yet another civilizational binary: Good AI belongs naturally to the “liberal,” “enlightened” rational societies of the “West.” The “East” is not to be trusted. When AI is harmful there, for instance, in Iran and China (but also in Russia), Western discourse frames it as a function of a retrograde political culture typical of the “Other,” thus rendered irrational. In this way, the myth of good AI allows Western institutions—including big tech companies—to claim a monopoly on ethical technological development, while externalizing harm to “illiberal” others.

Very much comparable to traditional Orientalism, the myth of good AI mobilizes desire—desire for progress, for mastery, for the rationalization of social life. At the same time, it displaces fear onto the “technological Other,” particularly to civilizations such as Iran and China, that have always had an exalted presence in the imagined “Western” narrative. Thus, the myth of good AI and techno-orientalism are co-constitutive. In this “Western” imagination, there is a fetish for “Asian efficiency” and “robotic perfection,” geared to a pathological fear of digital authoritarianism, framed with an increasing anxiety about Western decline. This angst about the resurgence of the “Other” animates cultural products, policy documents, think-tank reports, and media narratives.

This myth of good, “Western” AI relies on aspirational affects clearly discernible from the speeches of Elon Musk and others (for “Muskism” see Adib-Moghaddam 2025): A hysterical optimism about innovation, a religious belief in technological salvation, trust in the normative superiority of seemingly “Western” values such as capitalism and liberalism and a fundamentalist desire for the control of history, past, present, and future. These effects are incredibly dangerous for humanity, exactly because they constitute political reality and the fundamental friend-enemy distinction within societies and in international relations. The myths shape perceptions and, therefore, policies. They shape categories of threat and virtue. They determine which forms of violence become visible and which become normalized. In this sense, the myths surrounding AI are not peripheral discourses. They form the affective infrastructure of global technological politics.

Therefore, myths constitute an increasingly real delusion when they cease to be identified as false stories and transmute into symbolic architectures and techniques that organize society and political life. Techno-Orientalism functions exactly as a myth of Western technological virtue, producing a moral geography where the “West” remains the guardian of ethics and democratic progress, while the “East” is frozen as a site of either dystopian danger or monstrous hyper-modernity.

Techno-Orientalism as an affective myth is extremely potent. Such Techno-Orientalism legitimizes hybrid warfare, for instance, the recurrent attacks on Iran’s nuclear energy infrastructure. It prevents global technological governance, for example, the removal of legal barriers for AI research by Donald Trump and the US’s intransigence in governing AI internationally. Techno-Orientalism guides

export controls and sanctions such as the current US tariff regime and the comprehensive sanctions against Iran, Cuba, Venezuela, and other countries. It informs racialized policing and exploitative data extraction from marginalized communities within the “West” itself and in the Global South.

Decolonial Futures

What I have called critical AI studies suggests three pathways out of the current conundrum. First, the growing critical AI community needs to continuously challenge the myth that AI, and by implication technological innovation, belongs naturally to any one country or “civilization.” Our successful efforts in the humanities and the social sciences to dismantle notions of civilizational exceptionalism need to be transferred to the discourse about AI. We need to harass the “tech-bros” into compliance by the sheer weight of our intellectual argument in support of a form of “community AI” that serves human security.

Secondly, we need to “provincialize” the false moral authority inscribed into the Western narrative enveloping AI. The idea of the “West” has to be discarded in favor of a global reading of history, in general, and of the emerging AI universe, in particular. Only if we think of AI in universally human terms, rather than in a primitively tribal West-versus-the-rest dichotomy, can we tame the power excesses of private firms and states. Critical AI studies demand exposing this selective moral geography that the “West” has prided itself on for too long. Ancient cultures are reservoirs of a critical approach to AI, and these vast untapped sites of human knowledge can easily defeat ignorant delusions so typical of Orientalisms of any kind.

Such a movement, thirdly, foregrounds pluralistic human experiences and their technological cultures, epistemologies, and governance models, not as Ferrel deviations from the ideal “West” but as co-equal contributors to a common human experience. This means recognizing that ethical AI cannot emerge from a singular civilizational locus or template. Nor can AI be considered “good” simply because it originates from the geographical centers of global capitalism. As I have argued, Techno-Orientalism and the myth of good AI are not separate phenomena. They are intertwined mythologies that sustain global hierarchies, structure geopolitical anxieties, and shape perceptions of technological virtue and vice.

A critical engagement with AI requires precisely this kind of myth-diagnosis. We must understand how narratives produce power, how affects sustain hierarchies, and how the technological futures we imagine are inseparable from the political and social worlds we inhabit. I want to reiterate that our task is not merely to debunk these myths but to cultivate alternative imaginaries—ones that resist the civilizational binaries of Techno-Orientalism and the moral complacency of the “good AI” myth. Only then can we imagine technological futures that are genuinely plural, accountable, and humane. In this way, truly good AI emerges as a tool for global justice, rather than a mechanism of political domination and social exclusion. ♦

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